

NUMERICAL MODELING OF ADHESIVELY BONDED CFRP JOINTS CONSIDERING THE NON-LINEAR DEFORMATION OF THE ADHESIVE LAYERS

Shunta Mimura^{1*}, Takuma Abe², Takayuki Kusaka², Naoki Mori², Kiyoka Takagi³,
Masaki Hojo¹, Masaaki Nishikawa¹, and Naoki Matsuda¹

¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering and Science, Kyoto University, Kyoto 615-8192, Japan

² Department of Mechanical Engineering, Ritsumeikan University, Kusatsu, Japan

³ Integrated Defense & Space Systems, Mitsubishi Heavy Industries, Nishi-kasugai, Japan

* E-mail: mimura.shunta.44x@st.kyoto-u.ac.jp

Keywords: Adhesive joints, fracture mechanics, finite element analysis

ABSTRACT

Numerical analyses were conducted to investigate the detailed fracture behavior in the mode II fracture toughness test. Three models, including cohesive zone modeling (CZM) were used to evaluate the failure of an adhesive and an adherend, separately. The results showed that CZM can be used to accurately simulate crack extensions along the adhesive layer. The model with solid elements and zero-thickness cohesive elements can be used to effectively evaluate the failure of adherends, based on their shear stress distribution.

1 INTRODUCTION

Adhesive bonding techniques have been applied to various composite structures including components of aircrafts and auto-mobiles. The structural integrity of adhesive joints can be evaluated using fracture mechanics [1] [2]; and the evaluation of fracture toughness requires a sound understanding and knowledge of fracture behavior. However, little is known and understood about the non-linear behavior of adhesive layers. Therefore, there is a need for the development of a practical evaluation method for the evaluation of the non-linear behavior of adhesive joints.

In this study, the non-linear deformation in adhesive joints was investigated, and a practical evaluation method for fracture toughness was developed. In addition, the potential of numerical modeling methods to predict and analyze the fracture behavior of adhesively bonded structures, crack propagation in adhesive layers and adherend failure was investigated.

2 EXPERIMENTAL STUDIES

Two types of the end notch flexure (ENF) were investigated in this study (specimens are given in Fig. 1(a) and (b)). The specimen for the 4ENF test had a bending span, width, thickness of the adherends, and the thickness of the adhesive layer of $2L = 1000$ mm, $B = 25$ mm, $h = 10$ mm, $h_{ad} = 0.2$ mm, respectively. The 3ENF test specimen had a bending span, width, thickness of the adherends, and thickness of the adhesive layer of $2L = 200$ mm, $B = 20$ mm, $h = 3$ mm, $h_{ad} = 0.2$ mm, respectively. Specimens were fabricated using the unidirectional composite laminate, T800S/3900-2B (Toray), and the epoxy film adhesive, FM309-1 (Solvay).

The 4ENF test was conducted on the 4ENF specimen to obtain the reference value of the fracture toughness, G_{IIc} , because it had a long bending span which made it suitable for linear fracture mechanics tests and also for the evaluation of the crack surface friction. The 3ENF test was conducted to evaluate fracture toughness.

The fracture toughness, G_{IIc} , was calculated using the critical compliance method [3] considering the non-linear deformation of adhesive layers:

$$\frac{\delta^{cri}}{P^{cri}} = C^{cri} = \frac{3a^3 + 2L^3}{8EBh^3} + \frac{18hL - 9ha}{16GB(2h)^2} = \alpha a^3 + \beta a + \gamma \quad (1)$$

$$G_{IIc} = \frac{9P^2}{16B^2} \left\{ \frac{a^2}{Eh^3} - \frac{1}{8Gh} \right\} = \frac{P^2}{2B} (3\alpha a^2 + \beta) \quad (2)$$

In the above equation, δ^{cri} is displacement, P^{cri} is load of loading point during crack propagation, and α, β, γ are constants dependent on the material and geometric properties of the specimen. Crack growth resistance curves (R-curves) of the ENF tests are presented in Fig. 2. The fracture toughness of 4ENF was relatively constant during the crack extension, however, the behavior of 3ENF was different. The 3ENF had a relatively constant fracture toughness when the crack extension (Δa) was between 20 and 30 mm, and the initial increase in fracture toughness when the crack extension (Δa) was between 0 and 10 mm was due to the nonlinear deformation of the adhesive layer. The fracture toughness of 3ENF increased when the crack extension (Δa) was greater than 40 mm due to the local stress field near the loading point.

Figure 1: (a) Schematic of the 4ENF specimen. $2L = 1000$ mm, $B = 25$ mm, $h = 10$ mm, $h_{ad} = 0.2$ mm, respectively. (b) Schematic of the 3ENF specimen. $2L = 200$ mm, $B = 20$ mm, $h = 3$ mm, $h_{ad} = 0.2$ mm, respectively.

Figure 2: R-curves obtained from the experimental studies. Results of the 4ENF test (black line) and the 3ENF test (blue line).

The above results of 3ENF test were comparable to the theoretical results determined using equations (1) and (2) for the determination of fracture toughness, G_{IIc} .

3 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSES

3.1 Finite element models

Finite element analyses were performed to study the crack growth behavior of the 4ENF specimen, using three different types of models for the adhesive layer. The 4ENF specimen was analyzed using the finite element model in MSC. Marc 2017 software and the results are given in Fig. 3.

A model of 4ENF using the solid elements for the adhesive layer (Model S) is shown in Fig. 4 (a). In Model S the adhesive layer was assumed to be isotropic and elastic-plastic with a minimum element size of $0.16 \text{ mm} \times 0.16 \text{ mm}$ for the adherend, and $0.16 \text{ mm} \times 0.10 \text{ mm}$ for the adhesive. A model of 4ENF using the cohesive elements for the adhesive layer (Model C) is shown in Fig. 4 (b). In Model C the minimum size of the cohesive elements were $0.16 \text{ mm} \times 0.20 \text{ mm}$. A model using the solid elements of the adhesive layer and the cohesive elements along the assumed crack path (Model S + C) is shown in Fig. 4 (c). The adherends were assumed to be orthotropic and elastic for all the models and four-node plain strain elements were used. Fixed displacement of -50 mm in the y -direction was applied to the loading jig, and the loading point of the jig was fixed to move only in the y -direction from 0 mm to -50 mm . Friction between the specimen and the jig was neglected.

Figure 3: Schematics of the 4ENF model.

Figure 4: Finite element modeling for adhesive layers.

3.2 Mechanical properties of the materials

The mechanical properties of the adherend and the adhesive are given in Table 1. The stress-strain behavior of the adhesive is shown (red curve) in Fig. 5 (results from a compression test on bulk adhesive). The initial elastic modulus of adhesive, E_{ad} , is shown in Table 1, and the von Mises yield criterion was applied in the analysis.

In the Model C, the traction-separation law of cohesive elements shown in Fig. 6 was applied. Traction T_i and separation δ_i for the pure mode were related [4] by:

$$T_i = \begin{cases} \frac{2G_{c,i}}{\delta_{m,i}} \frac{\delta_i}{\delta_{c,i}} & \text{if } 0 \leq \delta_i \leq \delta_{c,i} \\ \frac{2G_{c,i}}{\delta_{m,i}} \frac{\delta_{m,i} - \delta_i}{\delta_{m,i} - \delta_{c,i}} & \text{if } \delta_{c,i} < \delta_i \leq \delta_{m,i} \\ 0 & \text{if } \delta_i > \delta_{m,i} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

E_1 [GPa]	E_2 [GPa]	G_{12} [GPa]	ν_{12}	E_{ad} [GPa]
135	7.2	3.6	0.34	1.96

Table 1: Material properties of adherend and adhesive.

Figure 5: Stress-strain curve of a bulk adhesive.

Figure 6: Traction law for cohesive elements.

In the above equation, where $\delta_{c,i}$ is the separation at the maximum traction $T_{max,i}$, and $\delta_{m,i}$ is the separation when the cohesive elements fracture and are damaged. $G_{c,i}$ is the fracture toughness of adhesive, which corresponds to the integral of the traction law and is given as:

$$G_{c,i} = \int_0^{\delta_{m,i}} T_i d\delta_i \quad (4)$$

Fracture toughness tests for mode II were conducted using the method proposed by Leffler, et al. [5], and the determined fracture toughness, G_{IIc} , was 5.3 kJ/m^2 . The fracture toughness for mode I was determined using the result of the experimental fracture toughness test and G_{Ic} was 1.5 kJ/m^2 . In the Model S + C, the fracture toughness was set to $G_{Ic} = 0.30 \text{ kJ/m}^2$ and $G_{IIc} = 1.1 \text{ kJ/m}^2$ to allow for uniform fracture of the cohesive elements. The penalty stiffness was defined as $E_I = T_{I\max}/\delta_{Ic}$, and was $3.0 \times 10^6 \text{ MPa/mm}$, hence, the elastic deformation of the cohesive elements was negligible in comparison to that of the solid elements.

3.3 Results and discussion

The load-displacement results are presented in Fig. 7. The crack onset of Model C was comparable to the experimental results, whereas in Model S + C it was at a lower load. The load-displacement relationship of Model C and Model S + C are comparable to relationship determined by the experimental results. Therefore, the macroscopic load-displacement behavior was successfully reproduced in each model.

A comparison of the crack propagation behavior is given in Fig. 8. The results show that the crack length increased as the displacement increased. The results of Model S + C were not comparable with the experimental result, however the results of Model C were comparable with the experimental results. The results suggest that Model C can be used to predict and analyze the fracture behavior of adhesive layers. The energy dissipation suggested by the results of Model S + C should be investigated further.

Figure 7: Comparison between the experimental result and the FEM analysis results of tests conducted on 4ENF.

The shear stress distribution along upper adherend-adhesive interface is presented in Fig. 9. The maximum shear stress of the mode II traction law, T_{II} , was set to 50 MPa , which was approximately equal to the maximum shear stress of the adhesive. The results suggest that the stress distribution in adherends can be predicted using the Model S and the Model S + C.

Figure 8: Crack propagation behavior results of 4ENF (determined by tests and by FEM analyses).

Figure 9: Shear stress distribution along adherend–adhesive interface of 4ENF using different FEM models.

4 CONCLUSIONS

End notched flexure tests were conducted to evaluate Mode II fracture toughness in adhesively bonded CFRP joints. The fracture toughness results of the 3ENF were comparable to the 4ENF. The results of the study showed that the method we proposed gave accurately determined fracture toughness, G_{IIc} . The behavior and mechanical properties of the 4ENF were simulated by finite element analysis using different models of the adhesive layer. The results of Model C were comparable to the experimental results and accurately predicted crack onset, whereas the Model S + C highly

underestimated the critical point. Crack propagation of Model C was also comparable to the experimental result, whereas the result of Model S + C underestimated crack propagation. The analysis results suggest that the stress distribution in adherends can be predicted using both Model S and Model S + C.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This paper is based on results obtained from a project commissioned by the New Energy and Industrial Technology Development Organization (NEDO).

REFERENCES

- [1] B.R.K. Blackman, A.J. Kinloch and M. Paraschi, The determination of the mode II adhesive fracture resistance, G_{IIc} , of structural adhesive joints: an effective crack length approach, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, **72**, 2005, pp. 877-897.
- [2] M.F.S.F. de Moura, R.D.S.G. Campilho and J.P.M. Gonçalves, Pure mode II fracture characterization of composite bonded joints, *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, **46**, 2009, pp. 1589-1595.
- [3] S. Inakazu, et al. JSME M&M 2018, OS0224, Fukui, Japan, 2018.
- [4] D.C. Noorman, "*Cohesive zone modelling in adhesively bonded joints: Analysis on crack propagation in adhesives and adherends*", 2014, pp. 27-40, Technical University of Delft.
- [5] K. Leffler, K.S. Alfredsson and U. Stigh, Shear behaviour of adhesive layers, *International Journal of Solid and Structures*, **44**, 2007, pp. 530-545.